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ISSN 2654-1823

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Publisher: SafeGreece [www.safegreece.org]

Editing, paging: Katerina – Navsika Katsetsiadou

Title: SafeAttica 2023 Proceedings

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SafeGreece Proceedings

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GEOSPATIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE PROTECTION OF THE EUROPEAN TERRITORY FROM ORGANIZED ENVIRONMENTAL CRIME (PERIVALLON PROJECT)

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the pressing concern of organized environmental crime in the EU, which is on the rise. With offenses increasing by 5-7% annually, traditional methods of detecting and investigating such crimes prove challenging. To combat this issue, the European Commission co-funds the PERIVALLON project, aiming to protect the European territory from environmental crime through intelligent threat detection tools. The project integrates cutting-edge technology, including Artificial Intelligence, geospatial intelligence, remote sensing, and multimodal analytics. It focuses on enhancing capacity building and international cooperation among security practitioners to address the growing environmental crime threat effectively. The main developments of this project are introduced in this paper, along with their relevance for combating environmental crime within the goals of EU, as well as their maturity level (concerning their technology readiness level).

Keywords: environmental crime, intelligent threat detection, geospatial intelligence, remote sensing, multimodal analytics.

1. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

Recent developments within the framework of the European Green Deal have aimed at criminalization and an overhaul of regulatory frameworks to address environmental crime and its effects on the financial interests of the EU. In this scene, the EMPACT priorities (2022-2025) highlight environmental crime as a major issue, with offenses increasing at an alarming rate [1]. Despite commendable efforts, the transnational nature of environmental crime and its convergence with organized crime, money laundering and corruption, have not been adequately integrated into current reforms [2]. The types of crime involved include intentional dumping of pollutants, illegal disposal of hazardous waste, cross-border trafficking of waste, and unlawful trade of HFCs. Conventional methods of detection and investigation are inadequate, necessitating advanced solutions for remote identification, evidence collection, and multimodal analysis.

The objective of this paper is to address the growing threat of organized environmental crime and its impact on the EU. Specifically, the research focuses on the ongoing PERIVALLON project, a European Commission co-funded project aimed at protecting the European territory from environmental crime through the use of intelligent threat detection tools. The project aims to develop an innovative environmental crime detection and investigation platform while enhancing capacity building and

international cooperation among security practitioners, including Police Authorities, Border Guards, and Regional and National Authorities [3].

2. METHOD AND DATA

The methodology of this paper starts by analyzing the nature and extent of organized environmental crime in the EU and identifying the key challenges in detecting and investigating such crimes. It further examines the specific objectives and the technological tools that are being developed within the context of the PERIVALLON project and their technological readiness level (TRL) [4]. Approximately 17 innovative components, most of them being around TRL 3-5 (Experimental proof of concept - Technology validated in relevant environment; with effective research and development already being validated through designed investigation) will form a unique platform forming a single-entry point for the end-users.

Data for this study primarily comes from various sources, including project documentation, reports, and academic literature on environmental crime and security. Information regarding the PERIVALLON platform's capabilities, which include automatic detection of waste disposal and pollutants, UAV-based site inspection, X-ray scanning, online monitoring, maritime routes prediction, and real-time risk assessment, are gathered from project resources and relevant publications.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The paper discusses the state-of-the-art at the advancements in combating environmental crime in EU and offers a brief look at the PERIVALLON project. By leveraging the latest technological innovations that support research in this field, such as Artificial Intelligence, remote sensing and geospatial intelligence, the (under development) platform enables more effective detection, investigation, and prevention of environmental crimes. The integration of multimodal sensor data, including satellite imagery, UAV-captured videos, and online information, strengthens decision-making for security practitioners in addressing environmental crimes.

Moreover, the Environmental Crime Observatory established by PERIVALLON provides comprehensive intelligence on environmental crime in Europe. The observatory identifies different types of environmental crime, their prevalence, societal impacts, and links to organized crime networks. The insights obtained from the observatory inform enhanced investigation processes and methodologies.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, organized environmental crime poses a significant threat to the EU, with offenses on the rise. The PERIVALLON project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe, addresses this issue by developing an innovative environmental crime detection and investigation platform. It also promotes capacity building and international cooperation among relevant security practitioners to combat environmental crime effectively. The project's cutting-edge technology and comprehensive intelligence through the Environmental Crime Observatory offer promising prospects for enhancing environmental security and defense in the EU.

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